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Review Article

NANOTECHNOLOGY IN DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMSTejal P. Bute*¹, Kalyani N. Sadafale¹, Aditya A. Unhale², Dr. Swati P. Deshmukh³.

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The developed field of nanotechnology will drastically alter the course of human history. Growing nanotechnology is expected to usher in "the Next Industrial Revolution," as some legislators and IT developers have even gone so far as to refer to it. Nonetheless, since nanotechnology is still in its infancy, opinions about its definition and fundamentals are far from universal. There are others who argue that nanotechnology is a distinct field of study and that it falls under the umbrella of general purpose technology (GPT). By delivering the medication to the site of action, controlled drug delivery systems (DDS) help reduce the drug's impact on important tissues and unwanted side effects. Lower drug dosages are necessary since DDS also prevents the medication from degrading or clearing too quickly and increases drug concentration in target tissues. Poor physiochemical characteristics in many promising novel compounds limit their solubility and biodistribution, preventing the medicine from interacting with the site of action. Low solubility at physiological pH and poor oral absorption of proteins and peptides, One barrier to drug development is the quick disposal of drugs and poor cellular absorption. Prospective drugs need to demonstrate that they can go to the site of action and produce an impact. Drug delivery research develops excipients, transporters, and solubilizers that deliver medications to their intended sites of action [1].

Keywords: Drug delivery, Gold nanoparticle, Magnetic nanoparticle, Ceremic Nanoparticle, Niosomes, Liposomes, Dendrimer, Nanoemulsion, Nanosuspension, Nanoparticle based on Solid lipid, Silica nanoparticle, Nanocrystal.

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INTRODUCTION:

The study, production, characterisation, and use of materials and devices whose smallest functional organization in at least one dimension is on the nanoscale scale (one-billionth of a meter) is known as Nanotechnology. Nanotechnology is a multidisciplinary scientific topic that has experienced tremendous development in the last few years [2]. The field of nanoscience and nanotechnologies holds great promise for improving human health care through a variety of applications, including medicine discovery, water purification, and the creation of lighter, stronger materials. Medical care for humans Research on nanotechnology has the potential to have a huge positive impact on health. The potential of profound advancements In medicine can be linked to the origins of nanotechnology. It has been demonstrated that nanotechnology can nano overcome the divide between biological and physical sciences by applying nanostructures and nanophases to a variety of scientific fields; in particular, nanomedicine and -based drug delivery systems, where these particles are very desirable. There are great hopes that the recently developed field of nanotechnology will drastically alter the course of human history. Growing nanotechnology is expected to usher in "the Next Industrial Revolution," as some legislators and IT developers have even gone so far as to refer to it. Nonetheless, since nanotechnology is still in its infancy, opinions about its definition and fundamentals are far from universal[3].

Types of Nanomaterials:**Gold Nanoparticle:**

The application of colloidal gold nanoparticles in the treatment of many illnesses such as cancer, multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, and neurological diseases like Alzheimer's disease, has been around for a while. The abilities of gold nanoparticles to conjugate with other bio mole without changing their biological characterisations, as well as their biocompatibility and ease of functionalization, are advantages. Crossing the blood brain barrier has been demonstrated for gold nanoparticles with sizes ≤ 50 nm. Through the permeable vasculature of tumor cells, PEGylated gold nanoparticles coupled with TNF (tumor necrosis factor) can enter. Gold Nanoparticles have a awesome commitment in cancer treatment, Diagnosis of cancerous cell and significance in the treatment of HIV [3].

Magnetic Nanoparticles:

Nanoparticles that are magnetized In the last several years, magnetic nanoparticles have grown to be one of the most researched and used forms of nanotechnology. Applications for magnetic

nanoparticles include gene transfer, cell separation, targeted medication delivery, and cell labeling. They are also used as contrast agents in magnetic resonance imaging (e.g., Feridex). Since iron oxide nanoparticles are biodegradable, biocompatible, and have superparamagnetic qualities that make them ideal for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) applications, they are being investigated extensively. There have been reports of drug-loaded magnetic nanoparticles that maintain their MRI characteristics. The anticancer drugs paclitaxel and doxorubicin were loaded onto iron oxide nanoparticles with up to 95% loading efficiency after being coated with oleic acid [3].

Ceramic nanoparticles:

Ceramic Small Particles Ceramic nanoparticles are the general term used to describe nanoparticles consisting of silica, titanium, alumina, and other materials. Many characteristics of these nanoparticles can be altered, such as their size, shape, porosity, inertness, and ability to connect to various proteins. They typically have a size of 50 nm. The acid labile model enzyme serratiopeptidase, hydrophobic therapeutic compounds, and increased DNA transfection efficiency (when combined with a DNA-dendrimer conjugate) have all been encapsulated in ceramic nanoparticles. Because of their osteoinductive and biocompatible qualities, ceramics have been used in bone tissue engineering. In 2009, Yamashita et al. examined the effects of smooth and rough surfaces of ceria stabilized zirconium dioxide, another ceramic material with potential as a material for dental implants, on the attachment growth of MC3T3-E1 cells, which are similar to murine osteoblasts. They compared their findings to those of the same cell line grown on titanium and pure alumina oxide [4].

Niosomes:

Noisome are vesicles made of non-ionic surfactant that resemble liposomes in form. They can serve as medication carriers and encapsulate aqueous solutes. Non-ionic amphiphiles self-assemble in aqueous media to produce niosomes. A closed bilayer structure can be achieved more easily by the use of heat or physical agitation. Because of their absorption by the liver and spleen, among other organs, niosomes are the most suitable drug delivery systems for conditions affecting these organs. They are employed to target cancer cells as well. Niosomal antigens are helpful adjuvants in the delivery of vaccines because they are strong stimulators of the humoral and cellular immune responses. When medications were delivered using niosomes as opposed to traditional methods, higher concentrations of the pharmaceuticals were discovered in the target region. They have also been utilized in conjunction with anti-inflammatory and anti-infective

medications. Oligonucleotide administration to cells has been accomplished with the use of PEGylated Categorical Niosomes.[5].

Liposomes:

spherical particles that encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic materials. Many strategies have been tried to achieve targetable properties, such as the noncovalent association of cell-specific antibodies with liposomes, the coating of liposomes with heat-aggregated immunoglobulins M(IgM), the covalent attachment of poly and monoclonal antibodies to the liposomes, the liposomes bearing glycoproteins, and the liposomes containing natural and synthetic glycolipids. Aqueous containing a dissolved medicine is captured by liposomes during vesicle formation, which is necessary for the passive encapsulation of water-soluble medications. Liposomes can be categorized as small unilamellar vesicles (SUVs), large unilamellar vesicles (LUVs), or multilamellar vesicles (MLVs) Several (up to fourteen) lipid layers arranged in an onion-like pattern and divided from one another by an aqueous solution layer make up multilamellar vesicles (MLVs). Several hundred nanometers is the diameter of these vesicles. Single-layered lipids envelop tiny unilamellar vesicles (SUVs), which range in diameter from 25 to 50 nm (some authors report as much as 100 nm). Truly speaking, large unilamellar vesicles (LUV) are a highly diverse class of vesicles that share a single lipid layer's outermost layer with SUVs. The liposomes' diameter ranges widely, spanning from 100 nm to the size of a cell (known as enormous vesicles). [6].

Dendrimers:

From the name "dendrimer," which comes from the fact that they are polymeric molecules made up of several precisely branching monomers that radiate outward from a central core in the shape of a tree. Trans-cellular, epithelial, or vascular biopermeability can be enhanced or resisted by dendrimer surfaces through functional design. For the encapsulation (i.e., interior isolation) of metals, small-molecule medications, or signaling groups, a well-defined interior void area within the dendrimer is appropriate [7]. Dendrimers can contain drug compounds by encapsulation or complexation. Research is being done on dendrimers for anticancer therapy, as well as for drug and gene delivery, including penicillin delivery. Polyamidoamines, polyamines, polyamides (polypeptides), poly(aryl ethers), polyesters, polysaccharides, and DNA are some of the often encountered forms of dendrimers in biological applications. The most widely used dendrimer scaffold is the polyamidoamine (PAMAM) dendrimers, which

come in a range of commercially available generations and auxiliary functions[8].

Carbon Nanomaterials:

In DDS, carbon nanocarriers are distinguished into two types: nanohorns (CNH) and nanotubes (CNTs). Recent studies indicate a similar carcinogenic potential of carbon nanotubes and asbestos. Carbon nanotubes have been shown to induce necrosis or apoptosis in macrophage cell lines as well as changes in cell morphology. Studied the effects of engineered carbon nanoparticles (MWCNTs and SWCNTs) on in vitro human platelet aggregation and in vivo vascular thrombosis in mice. Incubation of platelets with carbon nanomaterials resulted in platelet aggregation with little or no particle deposition. Incubation of bronchial epithelial cells and keratinocytes with high doses of SWCNTs causes oxidative stress, including ROS production, lipid peroxidation, and mitochondrial dysfunction [9].

Nanoparticles based on Solid lipid:

The three types of carrier systems that are based on solid lipid matrix that is, lipids that are solid at body temperature are solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN), nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC), and lipid drug conjugates (LDC). They have been used for distribution via the cutaneous, peroral, parenteral, ophthalmic, pulmonary, and rectal routes. Particles known as solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) are composed of solid lipids such as complex glyceride mixes, highly purified triglycerides, or waxes stabilized with different surfactants. In order to create a unique nanostructure with a higher payload and less drug ejection, solid and liquid lipids are combined to create NLC. Three types of NLC have been introduced: amorphous type NLC (drugs are protected from degradation by the surrounding solid lipid), multiple type NLC (drugs are solved in oils and free spaces for the accommodation of the guest molecules are formed by general imperfections in the matrix nanostructure), and imperfect type NLC [10].

Silica Nanoparticles:

Mesoporous silicon nanoparticles (MSNs), such as MCM-41 (Mobil Composition of Matter) and SBA-15 (Santa Barbara University mesoporous silica material), are another classification for silica materials employed in controlled drug delivery systems.

Their very porous structure, biocompatibility, and simplicity of functionalization are only a few of their many advantages as carrier systems. The most frequently selected carriers of inorganic nanoparticles for biological applications are silica materials. Diffusion typically regulates the release of drugs. Additionally, research has been done on the possible

use of silicalite and mesoporous silica nanoparticles in photodynamic treatment [11].

Polymeric Nanoparticles:

Structures that have a diameter of 10–100 nm are known as polymeric nanoparticles (PNPs). Natural polymers such as albumin, DNA, chitosan [51], and gelatine as well as synthetic polymers like poly-ε-caprolactone, polyacrylamide, and poly-acrylate are the sources of PNPs. PNPs can be categorized as biodegradable, such as poly(L-lactide) (PLA), polyglycolide (PGA), or non-biodegradable, such as polyurethane, based on their behaviour in vivo. Medication can either be encapsulated on PNP structure during a polymerization stage or immobilized on PNPs surface following a polymerization process. The biodegradable, thermoresponsive chitosan-g-poly(N-vinylcaprolactam)biopolymer, which is employed to transport 5-fluoro-uracil to cancer cells, is also noteworthy. Swelling followed by conformational changes during an LCST (lower critical solution temperature) transition is the proposed mechanism of 5-FU controlled release from this polymeric nanocarrier. It was noted that the toxicity to cancer cells was substantial, although not as severe as it was to normal cells. [12].

Nanocrystals:

A "clustering" of atoms, ranging in number between several hundred to tens of thousands, is what is known as a nanocrystal. The average size of these aggregates is between 10 and 400 nm, and their chemical and physical characteristics fall between those of bulk solids and molecules. Additional characteristics including bandgap, charge conductivity, crystalline structure, and melting temperature can be changed by adjusting the size and surface area. If bigger aggregates are to avoid developing, the crystals must be stabilized. By using nanosonication, nanocrystals are created [13].

Nanoemulsion / Microemulsions:

Oil, water, and a surfactant combine to form isotropic, thermodynamically stable systems called microemulsions. A microemulsion defining characteristic is thermodynamic stability rather than size, even if the droplet sizes are still less than 100 nm, frequently much less. They might have droplets that are between five and one hundred nanometers in size. Emulsions and microemulsions differ in that the latter are opaque combinations of two immiscible liquids that are thermodynamically unstable and typically need high torque mechanical mixing or homogenization to create scattered droplets in the 0.2–25 mm range. Both varieties are available as oil-in-

water (o/w) or water-in-oil (w/o). Several drawbacks include: (a) early drug leakage or release from incorporated drug; (b) phase inversion; (c) a large number of effective surfactants and/or co-surfactants lack a toxicity profile that is acceptable for pharmaceutical use; and (d) the development of complex systems, which can take a lot of time, is often necessary for microemulsion system.[14].

Nanosuspension:

Surfactants stabilize nanosuspensions, which are colloidal dispersions of insoluble molecular nanoparticles. Such medications can be kept in a crystalline form that is suitable for intravenous delivery by using nanosuspensions. Comparable to nanoemulsions, they have similar benefits. Also, because the medication is in a solid state, they can obtain even higher amounts of drug loading. Improved release and efficacy of medication delivery have been shown by numerous investigations utilizing nanosuspensions. Aggregates of several hundred to tens of thousands of atoms that come together to form a "cluster" are called nanocrystals. The typical size range for these aggregates is 10–400 nm, and their physical and chemical characteristics fall between those of molecules and bulk solids. The size and surface area can be adjusted to change the bandgap, charge conductivity, crystalline structure, and melting temperature, among other characteristics. To stop bigger aggregates from developing, the crystals need to be stabilized. Using nanosonication, nanocrystals are created. Prior to creating nanosized crystals, a high-speed stirring process creates a nanosuspension. This is followed by wet milling, high-pressure homogenization, nanocrystallization, and spray drying. The benefits of nanocrystallization include greater bioavailability, a significant reduction in dosage volume, an increase in the tolerable dose, and the capacity to solubilize poorly soluble medications [15].

Advantages of Nanotechnology:

The use of nanoparticles as a drug delivery mechanism has the following benefits.

1. The medication is released gradually and under control both during transportation and once it reaches its destination. Its organ distribution and subsequent clearance are also adjusted to improve the medication's therapeutic efficacy and lessen its adverse effects.
2. A key element in the drug's preservation is its ability to be integrated into the system without causing a chemical reaction.
3. It is easy to adjust controlled release and medication degradation properties.

4. Because there is no medication waste, the drug's bioavailability is improved at a particular location in the appropriate amount for an extended amount of time.
5. It increases the solubility of poorly soluble in water, decreases immunogenicity to extend the half-life of the drug's systemic circulation, releases the medication at a steady pace, and reduces the frequency of administration.
6. Compared to traditional methods, it enhances the drug's therapeutic efficacy while giving the patient comfort and compliance [16].

Disadvantages of Nanotechnology:

1. 1.It is inevitable that the nanoparticles would clash and group together into a bigger structure, which could compromise their ability to transport drugs. This drug carrier's small size allows the body's excretory pathways to remove it from the body. In animal tests, polymeric micelles have been shown to induce acute hypersensitivity reactions.
2. 2.Liposomes have certain disadvantages, such as being absorbed by the body's defense mechanism.
3. Larger nanoparticles can build up in important organs and cause toxicity that results in organ failure if they are not eliminated.
4. Researchers are still investigating the drug loading capability of liposomes, with no clear results.
5. 5.The build up of the nanoparticles in the skin and eyes following treatment was the outcome of all earlier research.
6. 6.The accumulation of gold nanoparticles in organs and bone joints; the need for external control to stop the nanoparticles from having negative consequences after they are injected into the body.

Application of Nanotechnology:

1. Investigating and Analyzing Biology Long
2. Tabbing of Nanoparticle
3. Nanostructured Materials
4. Single Molecule Detection
5. Protectective nanoparticle against pathogens
6. Nanotechnology in medicine & healthcare
7. Nanotechnology in imaging and diagnosis
8. Nanotechnologies for the treatment of cardiovascular –
9. Nanotechnology in cancer treatment
10. Nanotechnology in the treatment of diabetes
11. BioMEMS for insulin delivery [17].

CONCLUSION:

The purpose of nanocarriers as drug delivery systems is to enhance the therapeutic and pharmacological

properties of traditional medications. Incorporating drug molecules into nanocarriers not only provides targeted and controlled release, but also protects the drug from degradation. Nanocarriers can function at the cellular level and pass the blood-brain barrier (BBB) because of their small size. Nanocarrier-drug conjugates are more selective and efficacious than conventional drug conjugates. By collecting medications in target areas, they can lessen their toxicity and other negative side effects in normal tissues. As a result, fewer medication dosages are needed.

While many therapeutic agents based on nanoparticles are presently undergoing preclinical evaluation and development, there are only a few nanoparticle-based products on the pharmaceutical market, such as liposomal conjugates like daunoXome® (daunorubicin) and Doxil® (doxorubicin). This can be attributed to the numerous limitations and downsides of medication delivery systems based on nanoparticles.

Notwithstanding all of its drawbacks and restrictions, nanoparticle drug delivery systems (DDS) have the potential to alleviate a large number of the present drug delivery issues since they can react to even minute changes in the local cellular environment. Toxicological testing protocols, biocompatibility, drug loading, targeting, transport, and release, regulating interaction with biological barriers, detecting and monitoring exposure level, and environmental impact assessment must all be addressed before the ongoing research produces a clinically useful drug delivery system.

Only by doing meticulous research in the realm nanotherapy can a true therapeutic breakthrough be made. A successful cancer treatment may be achieved by the use of nanosystems in disease therapeutics. Moreover, drug carriers' selectivity is increased when homing devices—like folic acid, epidermal growth factor, or antibodies—are immobilized on the surface of nanoparticles. The two main uses of nanoparticles in medicine are target therapy and diagnosis, however there is still room for growth in this area.

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